

QUALITY CONTROL OF REFLECTIVE COATINGS ON THE REFLECTOR OF CAR HEADLIGHTS

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Abstract. *This study addresses the issue of ensuring the reliability and functionality of reflective coatings used in automotive headlight assemblies, focusing on one of the key performance parameters — the adhesion of the coating to the substrate. Adhesion strength determines the resistance of the reflective layer to external influences, including temperature fluctuations, vibrational loads, and chemically aggressive environments, which in turn directly impacts light distribution efficiency and road safety under low-light conditions. The study presents an analysis of existing methods for assessing coating adhesion strength, with particular emphasis on the tape test method, regulated by ASTM standards (notably ASTM D3330M, D3652M, and D3759M). The technological aspects of conducting the test are described, including two test modifications — cross-hatch cuts (Method A) and "X"-shaped incisions (Method B). The paper details the requirements for tape characteristics, sample preparation conditions (including preconditioning under climatic aging), and the procedures for interpreting the results. The experimental part of the research investigates the adhesion strength of aluminum coatings deposited by thermal evaporation in a vacuum (using the Arzuffi AM/KW 1900 system) on substrates of various automotive reflector models (Cobalt – 4NB, Onix – JBSC, Tracker – JBUC, Labo – B100, Damas – B150). The results confirm the high sensitivity of the tape test to changes in deposition parameters and substrate properties, making it a promising tool for process control and quality assurance in mass production environments.*

Keywords: *reflector models, tape characteristics, Perpendicular cuts, technological aspects.*

Introduction. Reflective coatings on headlight reflectors play an important role in ensuring quality road lighting during the night, and, as a result, vehicle safety during movement. For the reflective coating to perform its functional tasks, it is necessary to have good adhesion between the coating and the reflector base. This criterion is called adhesion. Quality control of coatings, based on the adhesion criterion, is one of the key aspects of ensuring quality, as it affects both the durability and functionality of automotive headlights. The adhesion of the reflective coating to the reflector surface is crucial for maintaining its efficiency and resistance to various external factors (temperature, vibration, chemical exposure).

Adhesion of the coating to the metal or plastic base of the headlight reflector is critical for ensuring the durability of the coating, maintaining reflective properties, and withstanding external influences. Low adhesion can lead to peeling or flaking of the coating, which worsens its reflective properties. As a result, this will reduce light output and worsen visibility on the road [1-2].

Materials and Methods. Several methods exist to assess the adhesion of the reflective coating to the base. The most common methods include the pull-off test, shear test, abrasion test, and tape test.

The tape test (or tape pull-off test) is one of the ways to determine the bond strength (adhesion) between the adhesive layer of the tape and the test surface (Figure 1). Several methods for conducting this test exist, but the basic idea is to apply the tape to the surface, press it down, and then quickly remove it to assess the force required to detach the tape. The results of the test can be used to compare the adhesion of different types of tape or evaluate the quality of bonding.

Figure 1. The process of determining adhesion parameters using the tape pull-off test.

This testing method is used to assess the adhesion properties of metal, plastic, and sealant before and after environmental exposure testing. The tape adhesion test is described using a crosshatch pattern and cross-cutting with cutting tools or guides. All paint systems and metal coatings must meet adhesion requirements when using the appropriate method. Unless otherwise specified, the dry film thickness will determine the necessary guiding tool or guide. If any of the methods (grid cuts, "X"-shaped cuts) are not applicable due to size and/or shape limitations (typically encountered with small parts), it is advisable to use alternative methods for determining the adhesion strength of the metal to the substrate.

It is crucial that the tape forms an adhesive bond with steel and aluminum in accordance with ASTM D3330M (ASTM - American Society for Testing and Materials) with a minimum peel strength of 760 N/m at 180 degrees. Weaker adhesives will reduce the accuracy of the test results. The tape backing should have low elongation.

Various parameters of the recommended tape are specified with the following sizes and characteristics: minimum width — 20 mm, total thickness — according to ASTM D3652M standard, more than 0.14 mm, adhesion (peel strength) to steel — according to ASTM D3330M standard, not less than 760 N/m, elongation — according to ASTM D3759M standard, maximum 5%, shelf life — maximum 12 months.

If the size or shape of the finished product does not allow for testing, the tests are conducted on specially prepared panels with coatings. The adhesion of organic coatings, determined by this method, is evaluated by the tendency of the coating to peel near the applied cuts.

Method A — Grid (mesh) cuts, Method B — "X"-shaped cuts.

Both methods require cutting the coating down to the base both before and after exposure to specified climatic conditions. To ensure high accuracy of results, sharp blades should be used, as blunt blades may cause vibrations, which, in turn, lead to measurement distortion.

Before testing, the samples in their original state should be thoroughly cleaned of contaminants and fully dried, if applicable. Since aluminum metallic coatings are produced in a vacuum, there is no need to clean the surface. Coatings obtained in a vacuum do not have

contaminants due to the principle of vacuum systems, which relates to environmentally clean technologies [3-4].

If specified in the methodology, the coated samples are pre-exposed to climatic conditions such as immersion in water, exposure to high humidity, salt fog, etc. Upon completion of the climatic exposure, the samples should also be dried by blotting.

To increase the reliability of the results, it may be necessary to conduct a series of tests (at least three) on different areas of the surface, which depends on the method validation requirements and the part size. The geometry of the product and its processing characteristics should be taken into account. The minimum recovery time for the sample after climatic exposure before testing should be at least 1 hour, unless otherwise stated in the regulatory documentation.

Method A — Grid (mesh) cuts

The tool used for making grid cuts (grid knife) must be inspected before starting work. If any damage or malfunction is found, the tool must be replaced.

Grid cuts are made with a sharp tool, as shown in Figure 2. The number of parallel lines and the distance between them depend on the coating thickness (Table 1). All cuts should be approximately 20 mm in length and made in a single, uniform pass with sufficient force to reach the substrate. Perpendicular cuts are made in the same way, intersecting at the center of the original lines.

Figure 2. Crosshatch Test. Method A
Table 1. Cutter spacing for test Method A

Film Thickness (microns)	Spacing (millimeters)	Number of Cuts (In each direction)
≤ 60	1	6
60 to 200	2	6
≥ 200	3	6

After the cuts are completed, the loose coating is removed from the surface with a soft brush or cloth napkin. A strip of tape approximately 75 mm in length is cut, avoiding contact with its adhesive side. The tape is applied diagonally over the grid, pressed firmly using an eraser to remove air bubbles and ensure a tight contact with the surface. After 5–10 seconds, the tape is sharply removed at a 90° angle to the surface. Adhesion is assessed according to Figure 3 and the scale from Table 2. The evaluation is conducted both on the surface of the sample and on the removed section of the tape.

Surface of crosscut area from which flaking has occurred Rating (classification)	None 0		Greater than 65% 5			
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Figure 3: Adhesion Performance for Test Method A (Crosshatch)

Table 2: Rating Scale Key for Test Method A (Crosshatch)

Rating	Description
0	The edges of the cuts are completely smooth; none of the squares of the lattice is detached.
1	Detachment of small flakes of the coating at the intersections of the cuts. Across cut area of 5% maximum is affected.
2	The coating has flaked along the edges and/or at the intersections of the cuts. Across cut area of 5% minimum but 15% maximum.
3	The coating has flaked along the edges of the cuts partly or wholly in large ribbons, and/or it has flaked partly or wholly on different parts of the squares. Across cut area of 15% minimum but 35% maximum is affected.
4	The coating has flaked along the degrees of the cuts in large ribbons and/or some squares have detached partly or wholly. Across cut area of 35% minimum but 65% maximum is affected.
5	A crosscut area of > 65% is affected

Method B — "X"-shaped cuts

The tool intended for making "X"-shaped cuts must be checked before use and replaced if there are any mechanical damages or signs of wear. Using a sharp knife, two intersecting cuts of 75 mm in length are made, as shown in Figure 4. If the painted surface area is insufficient, the decision on the applicability of the method is made by the responsible specialist. In case this method is used, the percentage of remaining coating is additionally specified (Figure 5). During the cutting process, the knife must be held strictly perpendicular to the surface, avoiding any lateral movements. When working with soft materials (e.g., polymers or sealants), the cuts should not reach a depth that could cause displacement of the substrate.

Figure 4: X-Cut Test (Method B)

Figure 5: X-Cut Test Small Area (Method B)

After making the cuts, the loose coating is removed with a soft brush or napkin. A strip of tape, 125–150 mm in length, is cut without touching its adhesive side. The tape is applied so that it completely covers the intersection of the cuts and extends at least 38 mm on each side at a 25°

angle, leaving a free end for gripping. The tape is pressed onto the surface with enough force to eliminate air bubbles. After 5–10 seconds, the tape is sharply removed in a vertical upward motion, strictly perpendicular to the surface. The evaluation is based on the area of the coating remaining on the 20×75 mm (1500 mm²) section. The analysis is carried out both on the surface of the sample and on the removed tape.

Results and Discussion. We conducted tests on the adhesion strength of aluminum coatings with a substrate using the "tape-test" method. For this, several samples of automotive headlight reflectors were selected, including Cobalt – 4NB, Onix – JBSC, Tracker – JBUC, Labo – B100, and Damas – B150. The coatings were obtained using the thermal evaporation system “Arzuffi, AM/KW 1900” (Figure 6). The deposition conditions for the aluminum coating were as follows: pressure in the vacuum chamber – 0.35 ± 0.2 MPa, cold substrate process time – 12-15 minutes. The sprayed element used was technically pure aluminum; grade Al-wire (chemical composition 99.8 – 99.99% of aluminum).

Tungsten wires (Figure 7), owing to their high melting point (melting point ≈ 3422 °C), were employed as heating elements for the evaporation of aluminum samples under vacuum conditions.

Figure 6. “Arzuffi, AM/KW 1900” vacuum installation

Conclusion

Ensuring the quality of coatings on automotive headlight reflectors based on adhesion criteria is an important component of quality control that directly affects the functionality, durability, and safety of automotive headlights. Regular use of adhesion assessment methods helps prevent issues related to coating delamination and a decrease in reflective properties, which in turn enhances safety and consumer satisfaction.

Based on the "tape-test" for determining the adhesion strength of aluminum coatings to the substrate, technological parameters of vacuum metallization equipment can be adjusted, which in turn allows for improved reflection quality of reflector.

Figure 7. Tungsten wire used for evaporation of aluminum (13 sm long) and aluminum wire samples

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